

ABDULLA ORIPOV AS A BRILLIANT REPRESENTATIVE OF UZBEK LITERATURE

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Abstract: *The article deals with valuable information about the brilliant representative of Uzbek literature Abdulla Oripov, his life and creative works. Moreover, peculiarities of poet's works are deeply discussed.*

Key words: *literature, masterpiece, bestowed, poetry, awarded, folklore, Proverbs, sayings, aphorisms.*

We know that sports and art can serve as the most important factor in promoting a country between countries. At the same time, literature not only enlightens the population of the country, but also serves to spread the history, culture and art of this country to other countries. It should be noted that Uzbek literature is distinguished by the presence of many bright representatives, as well as multifaceted creative products. Abdulla Aripov was such a beloved literary star and a versatile artist. Our favorite poet Abdulla Oripov was an poet, literary translator, and a politician. His the best work, masterpiece was the lyrics to the State Anthem of Uzbekistan. A part from writing his own poetry, Oripov translated the works of many famous foreign poets, such as Alexander Pushkin, Dante Alighieri, Nizami Ganjavi, and Taras Shevchenko, into the Uzbek language.

Oripov was not only a talented poet but also a statesman. He was a member of the Senate of Uzbekistan from 2005 until his death in 2016. He also served as the head of the Copyright Committee of Uzbekistan from 2000 until his death. He received many awards during his lifetime. Moreover, he became a National Poet of the Uzbek SSR in 1989. In 1998, he was awarded the title Hero of Uzbekistan, the highest honorary title that can be bestowed on a citizen by Uzbekistan. In addition to creating his own creations, he also translated the creations of brilliant foreign representatives such as Nikola Vaptsarov, Nikolay Nekrasov, Alexander Pushkin, Dante Alighieri, Harivansh Rai Bachchan, Jenő Heltai, Kersti Merilaas, Khalil Rza Uluturk, Lesya Ukrainka, , Qaysin Quli, Nizami Ganjavi, Sergey Baruzdin, Taras Shevchenko, and Yeghishe Charents, into the Uzbek language. In particular, he translated Dante's Divine Comedy into Uzbek. Oripov's own works in Uzbek have been translated into Russian and many other languages. Oripov received many awards during his lifetime. In 1983, he was awarded the State Hamza Prize. In 1989, he became a National Poet of the Uzbek SSR. In 1992, he received the

prestigious Alisher Navoiy State Prize. In 1998, he was awarded the title Hero of Uzbekistan, the highest honorary title that can be bestowed on a citizen by Uzbekistan.

The special study of Abdulla Aripov's works, which express human life, his dreams and aspirations at a high artistic level, and have obvious signs of universal poetic thinking is one of the most important issues in today's literary science. In his poems, the poet chooses a form that fits the artistic content. The folk spirit in art is perceived in harmony with the motives of folklore, the guiding principles of folk art thinking, which have accompanied mankind for thousands of years.. The poetic word has a special place in the works of poetry, which are the most vivid, expressive and concise form of figurative thinking. When a poet uses simple words with certain adjectives or phrases, unexpected meanings, extraordinarily moving, flowing verses emerge. After all, the poems of the poet Abdulla Oripov embody the words and meanings that are as soft as silk, as fragrant as musk, as sharp as a dagger. The poet tries to expand the meaning of the word, using the opportunities of the native language. The poet, who is able to see with his own eyes the richness of his native language vocabulary, polished like a string of pearls, chooses every word with taste; measured on the scales of thinking. At the heart of the original and figurative method of expression lies artistic logic; of course, this logic comes in a concise and free of any artificial ornaments. In the realization of this form, we see, first of all, the harmony of the poet's preference, thinking and sharp-sighted eyes. In fact, as a result of observing the life of the people, the life experience, conclusions about the sociopsychological conditions, logical generalizations appear in the oral tradition. Proverbs, sayings, aphorisms are passed down from generation to generation and live in the artistic thinking of the nation. In such wise expressions, analogies (metaphors and similes), comparisons (antithesis), parallelism, irony, pitching and other means of artistic expression are widely used. Abdulla Aripov's poetry, of course, has such imagery.

To sum up all given information we should highlighted that, in the verses, the vocabulary of our native language is presented in all its splendor. The expression of emotion and reality in the poem is logical, coherent, complementary, and highly artistic, revealing the foundations of social processes. Thus, the poetic study of the language of Abdulla Aripov's poetry can be carried out in several aspects, and in each of them the unique poetic perception of the artist, the skill of using poetic words is shown. The poet's deep philosophical spirit seems to have a high expressiveness in the use of poetic words in his poetry, which is in harmony with the weighty folk artistic sensitivity.

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